

- ☰ Batman Zero Lima Force
- The Resilient Way - American Institute

Comparing Operators' Total Skill Level (v1) (XP, SQ or CQ)

MESS 0042

MIMS 2.8.41¹ - Inventory of Special Operator Skills; using the famous fictional operators to develop a realistic comparison tool for real-world skillsets in special forces and black ops

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the author goes over a whimsical/mimsical inventory that was created which turned out to support choices made in science fiction writing. The inventory has some useful data in it, however, describing how we can make better special operators, with areas to grow in, and of course correlate to both the story, and to modern soldier futurization.

Keywords: Future Soldier - Anime - Special Operators - Video Game - Tom Clancy's - Spies - fiction

¹ ☰ SpecOps Skill/Ranking

- Figure 1 (cover) - Total Skillpoints vs. characters
- Figure 2 (pg 2-4) - Skillpoints by character, with Team Origin

Introduction

When the author wrote the fanfiction, “Batman - Zero Lima Force,” he didn’t have a particular intention. He was writing it “stream of consciousness,” and also had some ideas he wished to convey. It is an adult-level MIMSical fan-fiction, in the genre of science fiction and action. Many of the influential properties, whether they are Marvel, DC, anime, or Tom Clancy’s, were based on special operations. The author admits he is neither specops/special forces, nor an expert in operations. Therefore there is a great limit to the style of writing, and there is no comparison to a Mark Greany or Tom Clancy, etc. There is a plethora of fan-art, and internet nonsense, as well as the R-rated components. The work cannot possibly be funded, it has way too many connections to licensed properties. However, its chief benefits were in the conveyance of new science fictions (since so many corporate written properties are less like the “Expanse” and “See” and more like less creative properties like “Mandalorian” or “the Peripheral.” Ie - rehashes), and in new technologies, or frightening possibilities of Hellish philosophies that go unabated. Also, it provides a new level of benefit in terms of strategic thinking, since right now various Velikoskesque psychic limitations exist with regards to how mankind is dealing with past and future catastrophes, potential aliens, hyperdimensional, existential and cognitive threats, spatial(geo)-politics, and of course medicine, food, and other essentials that in the past Nature provided and now we rely on ourselves (MIMS).

The Inventory

The basic question arose, “Who is tougher, Rambo or Dutch?” Of course, there was no direct way to answer this, even though the operators are from the same era of thought. More recently, Gray Man and James Reece (“Terminal List”) have shown increased coherence to realistic frameworks, and yet it is not mimsically proven that this is better than the use of super-charged archetypes (of which in this study Arnold Schwarzenegger played **three** roles!)² However, the Japanese have made cybernetic/transhumanist operators that (clearly) surpass these American Icons, and yet, what is the real aim? To imagine the next level of human development! What does it say to us that these are all hyper-violent individuals? It certainly challenges the ridiculousness of pacifism, and supports the idea of violence as a MIMS³. But it unfortunately is difficult to remove the expression from the ex-post-facto of the gods-driven modern society, especially in the wake of the power of the Marvel Cinematic Universe, or at least, comic books as the main medium of archetypal conveyance.

However, the author was mulling over the Resilient Way American Institute’s New Soldier design and augmentation, considering the role of the Ghost Recon: Future Soldier⁴, and various technologies, and also of the past forays into the super-soldier concepts, and (of course) Kung Fu⁵... and he asked “What would an inventory look like?” What would, after all, a top-tier “best of the best... of the best” modern ninja warrior look like? There are limits to boxing and MMA. Even the author’s “springing style” boxing, and Lomachenko’s “the

² Do not miss the fact that Arnold, a classic narcissistic overachiever, was the former Mr. Olympian record holder and is still widely considered the Greatest of All-time in body-building for these achievements and his mentalism displaying in “Pumping Iron.” He even became governor for 8 years. These are not easy feats for mortal men.

³ MESS0010: MIMS 2.81 - Violence as a MIMS

⁴ GHOST RECON FUTURE SOLDIER Gameplay Walkthrough Part 1 FULL GAME [4K 60FPS PC] - No Commentary

⁵ <https://careagaangel.wixsite.com/wutaodi>

matrix” style of ‘4D’ fighting⁶ is inadequate to explain the full concept. There is the consideration of cyberization, integration, socialization, competency, resiliency, the full incorporation of Total Shi, and the methods of the Art of War (bingfa)... all things which were super inherent in Historical Martial Arts, particularly HEMA⁷ and Bushido, but haven’t been fully considered - even by SOCOM - until very recently.

In this inventory, there are 1,000 points possible, and then each of the 10 categories have 100 points possible. Therefore each inventory item is unique and is actually an array. Unfortunately, the author is relying upon the imprecision of relative inventory comparisons *between* characters. Also, some items seem to “start” at 10 and decrease, and others to start at 0 and increase. There is an issue with too few properties (like “Commando” being our only real glimpse into the personally of an iconic operator, “Matrix”)⁸ or too many with conflicting details. This is important because these types of properties act as propaganda and recruiting instruments, as well as ways young men (and now women) shape themselves for future scenarios and combat. What one thinks about, expands. So what is offered?

The irony of the clearly “OP” (overpowered) offerings of the Japanese icons of “the Major” and “Solid Snake” is that the people that obsess about them rarely have lived “high-performance” lives (the author has at least become a multi black belt in Shaolin gongfu and mastered boxing and grappling). Many of them are fat losers in their mothers’ basements. However, all the more reason for them, and the creators of the properties, to be trusted for their imagination. For example, while the Major (Kusanagi) lacks the ultimate siege ability of a James Bond or John Matrix or Rambo... she scores extremely high in technical IQ (TIQ) related issues, such as hacking, electronics, etc. Therefore, she has a more complete package, and is after all quite strong (because of her fully cyberized body). However, isn’t it interesting that she did not come in first place?

The Zero Lima Force ... affirmed

The book was written from April to September, 2022. This inventory was performed in late November 2022, and the two were not related works. However, an interesting thing happened that caused some cross-over and may cause many to wonder about favoritism and data quality. The top scorers⁹ in the group (though the author was watching the “Bourne” series ... and “See” at the time) were:

1. Snake (“Metal Gear Solid”)	-	Video Game	-	611
2. Major (“Ghost in the Shell”)	-	Anime	-	604
3. Nomad (“Ghost Recon”) ¹⁰	-	Video Game	-	580
4. Sam Fisher (“Splinter Cell”)	-	Video Game	-	566

These are the primary recruits of the Batman - ZLF unit, for the reason that they are the top operators of their respective fields. Also, the book is set in the future and most of the other operators are dead or long retired at least. There is a need for top operations, and top cyber capabilities. It’s a fact that the non-Clancy’s American operators ... and the “dinosaur” James Bond... are not ideal candidates for Batman’s needs. His first operation, outside of hacking and stealing from Wakanda - an incredibly dangerous place which the CIA didn’t even know existed (in the MCU): to break into Cheyenne Mountain/NORAD to defeat the ‘Ub3r-Hitler.’

⁶ Normal 2 directions, + any part of the body from any angle and + wrestling/acrobatics/upside down.

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Historical_European_martial_arts

⁸ Same with Dutch in “Predator”, although he is very well developed in this. The two are incredibly similar but different in key, strategic ways.

⁹ Note the lower scorers are movie or book characters. More ‘grounded’.

¹⁰ A supposed secret outfit of the US Army’s “Green Berets”... already a Next^{Next} level unit; hence: Future Soldier. Good job UbiSoft... you can thank Clancy’s mimsicality!

To operate with that type of anti-Terminator type proficiency, Batman (now fully cyberized himself) required a team of time-tested and precise individuals of a “particular set of skills” (to borrow from “Taken”).

So the author feels this isn’t data creep, but re-affirmation that there are scientific reasons for Batman’s choice. The deduction here, however, definitely follows after the induction/intuition of the original book. That... is intriguing, if nothing else.

Wasted Talents?

What about the other operators? How do we go about comparing the top SEALs, and top CIA people? We look at their works, and really compare them. Both Bourne and Gray Man are touted as the supreme type warriors, but compared to Aaron Cross’ drug-enhanced systemic approach, or to Bond’s lucky-plucky-kill everything for “Queen and Country”... we don’t see that they have the longevity or skill to match the hype. Fans will storm, and argue, but the data is pretty clear.

Compared, too, to the raw power of the top big-name operators such as Rambo, and their philosophy of the Mind being the greatest weapon, well it is easy to see that there are major limits.

The exceptions appear to be the pure spies (like Hunt and Tasker), who can obviously do missions no one else can... save Bond whose luck is impossible to teach or train... and this makes them indispensable operators.

Few of the above are excellent team operators as well, and Reece has the greatest advantage here. But none of the “go to 11” on teamwork, and this is probably a reflection of the “rugged individualist” in sci-fi MIMS. It shows a weakness in understanding the specops community in general. All specops tend to rely on thoughtful, individualists who are excellent team players and rely on one another. Spies are individual operators, but at least have a strong COC/System to back them up. Gray Man exists almost without one, and this makes him less effective, ultimately, than Ethan Hunt... who at least half the time has the Mission Impossible Force. Also the splinter cells, like Sam Fisher have Echelon - a division of the NSA - which at least most of the time is in support. But it is the relentless skill growth of Nomad, as well as a very well-rounded personality and set of missions, which gives the Ghost Recons such a promising advantage, without the “cheats” of Japanese mimsical technologies from the “almost here”... which are obviously *not here yet* for the spec ops soldier, to date.

Maybe they are, and the public isn’t told about it. The author hopes so. But the author fears that the New Axis - China and Russia - will steal the Future Combat Systems¹¹ and other ideas, and develop these soldiers, on a backbone of gongfu and ninjutsu-like discipline, and achieve the technical mimsicality *first*. This would be problematic, if we (in America/NATO/West) rely on the braun and pure brutality and strengths of our muscle-bound operators. **Low TIQ lost this inventory**, and not for lack of brain power/IQ. Bourne and Cross are super intelligent. Rambo is no dummy. Matrix seems smarter than Bond, if not as perspicacious. However, all of these pale compared to the Japanese and Clancy’s operators.

Going to 11

So few of the main operators exuded a ridiculousness in any particular category as to be said they “go to 11.” However, those that did appear related to the muscle-bound next-level achievers of Stallone and Arnold. Those characters exude a masculine charm which is hard to escape the gravity-well of. However, in the end, it was Rambo’s next level survivalism that gave him an edge over his other non-computer savvy muscle-bound

¹¹ America’s New Tank Needs to Chill Out

operators. That, and he could fly. Although at least Dutch could deal with an alien threat. Why do so few of the operators know how to deal with alien threats... if we are so concerned about aliens and UFOs to begin with? A wider study is recommended, among the nerdy populace.

Figures 3-6: Rambo, Dutch, Matrix, and Nomad¹² ; the ultimate brutal specops commandos.

¹² [THE LONE SOLDIER | Solo Stealth & Epic \[4K UHD 60FPS\] Ghost Recon Breakpoint Gameplay | No HUD](#)

Basic Skills, Survival Skills, Computer Skills, CQC, Physical Abilities...

Basic Skills, Survival Skills, Computer Skills, CQC, Physical Abilities...

Figure 7 & 8 - Skills by Operator, and Operator by Skills; purple lines as baseline

Basic skills add up

The Major doesn't just score high in computer and electronics skillsets, she scores high in Basic skills, CQC, and Versatility. In other words, she's very well-rounded as an operator, even if she isn't good with kids or very lucky. She is an extremely effective leader of other high-performance operators (Section 6), and therefore scores high in teamwork. She's a well-packaged individual, and well battle-hardened as a soldier (a colonel).

The other operators that score high in basic skills tend to do best overall, such as Snake, Ethan Hunt (who scored the highest), Nomad, and Fisher. Then there are the Navy SEALs. The entire premise of a SEAL is that they are proficient at sea, in air, or on land. They are also excellently trained at computers and electronics, and have great teamwork. However, in medicine, and ninja skills, and surprisingly versatility, they could do better. It may very well be that this is the foibles of these characters, and not the SEALs organization really. John Clark, in particular, is quite stodgy. And Reece, unfortunately for him, has brain damage and memory issues. He's not at his best, though his toughness is second to none. Both SEALs "go to 11" in areas such as willpower, or "in the shit." People who are capable of going through what John Clark went through, both in Vietnam and afterwards, and especially as a team leader of Rainbow Six and later at the twilight of his stellar career: The Campus.

Survivalness, Resiliency, and Reliability

If one needed to run an op, well Hunt, Cort (Gray Man), or one of the Japanese operators will do a super fine job. But there's something about the reliability and tenacity of Rambo, Nomad, or Clark that is so attractive. Reece and Fisher are also fine choices, and it's hard to say anyone can survive a more hardcore FUBAR situation than Dutch. But the scores for Rambo, Clark, and especially Nomad really show that these resiliency skillsets, combined with basic skills, make for excellent predictors of unstoppable operators. We must safely assume, therefore, that the best predictor for a special forces/ops soldier is precisely what the SEALs are famous for testing and training: a special 'it' that weeds out the quitters, and if the operator can survive - indefinitely - in the wilds, then they are almost certain to have this X-factor. However, they simply need more computer skills, and CQC training, to compete with the top anime/gamer stars out of Japan. A deeper, wider study - as mentioned before - of literature and other franchises will lead to an increased chance of finding an operator that exceeds 700 or even 800 points. One has to wonder how would Batman score?

Let us, right now, as we write, put together a special tab just for Bruce Wayne (though he is a superhero, and not an operator).

Yes, we see that indeed Batman has a higher skill average (7.45), and an overall score of 724 with an outstanding 9.3 in computer skills. That's ... insane, really. And it speaks volumes to the reasons why he is the mental leader of the Justice League, even though he is without superpowers. Like Sherlock Holmes, his mind - and the corpus of work describing him - is voluminous, and decades-old (approaching 100 years). This makes a big difference in character development, and in actual development. In the author's book, of course he is even over 100 years old and is fully cyberized. His mentality is what makes him timelessly formidable. And he's even pretty decent with children, and has psychedelic experience (and a plethora of alien experience). In short, he can be shellshocked and overcome it quite easily, due to the fortifications of his mind. The Chinese identified this as a "thick face" type of mentality, and is exemplified in particular folk heroes, such as Wu Song (who killed the tiger), and others who were able to overcome much through the efforts of their minds.

This inventory needs more refinement, but the author has found it very enlightening, indeed. It also might have little deep meaning or developmental use. The armed services can consider it when developing their next-level soldiers.

The B Team

Comparing The B Team's Total Skill Level (v1) (XP, SQ or CQ)

Figure 9 - The B Team (at least ... a second inventory); credit: author

People began asking the author, while this was in edit, about certain names. Also, it's always nice to have more data points. Particularly people thought (as the author did) that at least Casey Ryback and Bob Swagger would do well; as well of course as one would expect Captain America, Wolverine (as Weapon X), and the A Team - a whole team - would. And, to a limit, they did. It was the author's interest, also, to compare McCoy's delta force skills with Matrix, and to compare (for fun), McClane ("Die Hard") with Riggs ("Lethal Weapon").

One of the main intrigues of these individuals was a higher number of times they "went to 11" and yet they still couldn't attain (for the most part) equivalent numbers. The problem is - it seems - either few films, or monodimensional character design (like Captain America), or other problems in the character. Wolverine, for example, has numerous psychological hindrances. But the police characters are excellent examples of under-designed operators. Plissken probably suffers from a bad second film, but he did pick up key skill XP in that film, and it expanded him. He's just monodimensional. It is expected that the children's operator - GI Joe Sergeant Slaughter - would do poorly. It's interesting that the entire A Team did less well than specifically engineered operators like Rambo or Cort Gentry - the Gray Man. As for team comparison:

Avg Score vs. Organization

Figure 10: XP averages by organization

Figure 11: XP comparison by special program

Figure 12: Sample size comparisons by organization, with exact XP shown. Credit: author

Conclusion

Batman is a superhero with no superpower; just an inherited superdetective skill of Sherlock Holmes.¹³ He is uber-developed. Among those he chose from, he chose well in the author’s story for the Zero Lima Force.

The main conclusions, though, have more to do with the data, and with the idea of how SOCOM and JSOC choose to guide the branches of the military on how to “design” special operators. How they design them determines the literature, which then acts as a bit of a propaganda and informancy effort to the young public/men, who become operators 10-20 years later.

Also, it is clear that:

- Computerization/cyber/electronics matters
- Basic and Survival skills > strength
- Teamwork makes the Dream work
- Willpower and experience have no replacements in XP
- Team players and leaders are more XP, even OP
- Brutal killing machines only get you so far in character design
- Future Soldiers do better than relics and old school players
- Luck is important, but not as important as collected skill
- A mutated weapon is better than a monodimensional supersoldier
- Being shock proof is important, but dealing with fatigue and injury, and preventing injury is more important
- Video game and anime/esque characters are often better developed/OP
- Clancy’s characters are more developed, especially Nomad, Fisher, and Clark
- The SEALs are perhaps overhyped, and the Delta Force is underhyped, due to differences in their publicity; **writers do not understand Delta Force**
- The CIA operatives are definitely OP; the Japanese characters are based on futurization.
- Special Programs at a major improvement to XP levels
- Spies do better than cops
- The myth of the Army infantry NCO exceeding the skill XP of an Army Ranger remains prevalent in the minds and hearts of action nuts.

Figure 13, Score vs. Name

¹³ MIMS 2.10.1-3 - MESS0025: Investigation - Sir Arthur's Gift

Spec Ops Inventories

Figure 14 - Skills 8 and above, by Operator (made with Excel); credit: author

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Appendix - Badass Operatives Pics & Gifs

